

Fake News Detection Framework using Multi-Features and Dual Emotion Signals

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Abstract. The proliferation of fake news on social networks poses a serious threat to the ecology of social information dissemination, often evoking emotions such as fear and sadness among users. This phenomenon underscores the need for automated fake news detection systems that leverage emotional features to effectively mitigate its detrimental impact on society. Several researchers have addressed emerging challenges in fake news detection by analysing a range of features including emotional signals and employing diverse computational techniques. Furthermore, when leveraging dual emotional signals (publisher and social emotions) hold significant potential for fake news detection, but have received limited attention in existing studies. Our primary objective is to amalgamate diverse features by systematically analyzing each framework to enhance fake news detection. In this paper, we introduce a deep learning framework called *Dual Emotion-based Fake Information/News Detection* (DE-FIND) that integrates dual emotion signals, classified under affective features, in conjunction with semantic and structural propagation features. The proposed framework demonstrates superior performance over baseline methods across standard benchmark metrics on real-world dataset.

Keywords: Social media analysis · Sentiment analysis · Deep Learning · Multi-Features · Fake news detection.

1 Introduction

The widespread dissemination of fake news poses significant threats to societal stability and erodes public trust in information systems. The rapid spread of misinformation through Online Social Networks (OSNs) has amplified the impact of political content, conspiracy theories, and misinformation related to global pandemics, all of which significantly influence people’s daily social interactions, lifestyles, and overall behaviour. These various forms of fake news misguide public trust and social stability in critical situations, fostering distrust toward governments, researchers, and economic markets. Therefore, developing effective and scalable automated fake news detection systems has become a critical priority. In response, researchers have increasingly focused on developing automated fake news detection methods that leverage natural language processing,

social context analysis, and emotional signals. However, despite growing interest, current approaches often overlook the nuanced role of emotion, especially dual emotional signals from both publishers and commenters, which can significantly affect how false information spreads and is perceived.

In the midst of ongoing global challenges, sentiment and emotion are widely recognized as the dominant drivers of human behaviour [11]. Gaining insight into the emotional drivers behind the spread of fake news is essential for formulating effective interventions to reduce its harmful effects on social media platforms. Fake news is often crafted to elicit emotional responses from readers, potentially influencing specific behaviours and interactions between publishers and commenters. Hence, incorporating dual emotional signals is a crucial step in acknowledging the importance of diverse emotional perspectives in identifying misinformation, i.e., both publisher emotion and social emotion. In this regard, Guo et al. [8] introduced a novel framework called Emotion-based Fake News Detection (EFN), which utilizes a deep neural network to extract representations from publisher emotion, social emotion, and textual content, highlighting the critical role of dual emotional perspectives in improving detection accuracy. Similarly, Zhang et al. [22] proposed a dual emotion-based plug-in to enhance existing fake news detection frameworks by incorporating both publisher and social emotional cues. Recently, Luvembe et al. [12] introduced a deep normalized attention mechanism to enrich the extraction of dual emotion features, alongside an Adaptive Genetic Weight Update–Random Forest (AGWu-RF) approach aimed at boosting the accuracy of fake news detection. However, incorporating dual emotional signals is a critical yet under-explored aspect that can significantly improve fake news detection.

In addition, emotionally charged fake news, particularly content that evokes fear, anger, or excitement, tends to propagate more rapidly across social media platforms due to its heightened psychological impact. According to Zaeem et al. [20], negative sentiment in fake news spreads more quickly across social networks compared to the slower diffusion of true news carrying positive sentiment. To enhance the performance of fake news detection models, it is essential to investigate the temporal dynamics of emotional information [19] and to extract semantic features related to information propagation within social network texts [21]. As part of this research, the study [15] examines the interplay between emotion information and information diffusion to develop interventions that promote critical thinking, media literacy, and responsible sharing practices. Therefore, detecting fake news and systematically examining public emotions by understanding their propagation patterns remains a significant and worthwhile area of exploration.

The study of false information and/or fake news typically falls into two main domains [18]: technical approaches [3] (i.e., automatic detection of fake news by leveraging NLP, and pre-trained language models like BERT, RoBERTa etc.) and behavioural analysis [9] (i.e., examining factors like belief, attitude, and intention to understand how false claims influence opinion formation and decision-making.). In this paper, our study bridges both technical and behavioural research by detecting fake news using a pre-trained language model and simul-

taneously analysing public duel emotions in response to such information. To leverage emotional information for fake news detection, we define two distinct types of emotions: (1) *Publisher emotion*: the emotion expressed by the original author at the time of posting the content on social media; and (2) *Social emotion*: the collective emotional responses expressed by users as the information propagates through the network [8]. While existing studies [12,22,8,10] have explored dual emotion signals, semantic content, and propagation patterns independently or in partial combinations. On the contrary, a comprehensive multi-task learning framework that systematically integrates dual emotions (publisher and social), semantic representations, and structural propagation features for detecting fake/true news remains largely unexplored. To the best of our knowledge, no prior work has holistically combined these three dimensions within a unified framework and the combination of technical and behavioural research still needs to be explored properly.

To address these gaps, we propose a novel model that integrates multiple features, including dual emotion, semantic, and structural characteristics referred to as *Dual Emotion-based Fake Information/News Detection* (DE-FIND). To model dual emotions and capture both emotional resonance and dissonance for fake news detection, we propose *duel emotion* features that jointly represent publisher emotion, social emotion, and the similarity or divergence between them. To extract *semantic* features, we utilize the Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [4] pre-trained language model. Additionally, the proposed model captures propagation of *structural* features through the use of Bidirectional Graph Convolutional Networks (Bi-GCNs) [2]. The effectiveness of the proposed approach is demonstrated through analysis of various topics using publicly available X datasets (previously known as Twitter). The key contributions of this paper are as follows:

- We present a principled approach to capture both publisher and social emotion signals, demonstrating the significance of these emotional dimensions from multiple perspectives in enhancing fake news detection.
- We introduce a deep learning framework DE-FIND that performs fake news detection by extracting of dual emotion signals, semantic content, and structural propagation features.

2 Overall Architecture of the Model

To overcome the limitations of existing fake news detection approaches, we propose a deep learning framework called *Dual Emotion-based Fake Information/News Detection* (DE-FIND) model. Fig. 1 illustrates the overall architecture of the proposed model, which is categorized into multiple deep learning components namely (1) *Emotion-based temporal propagation*, (2) *DualEmo feature extraction*, (3) *Semantic feature extraction*, (4) *Structural feature extraction* and (5) *Fake news detection*.

Fig. 1. General view of DE-FIND model

2.1 Emotion-based Temporal Propagation

To effectively study emotion diffusion and behavioural impact on social media, we have formulated *Emotion-based Temporal Propagation* based on temporal conversation and different emotion states of the user by analysing *content-based*, *user-based* and *emotion-based* features.

Given a direct graph $G = (V, E)$, where each vertex $u \in V$ represents a post, which can be a tweet or a reaction C_i . An edge $(u, v) \in E$ denotes a reaction v to post u . Every vertex of the user u_i in the temporal propagation contains emotion state $S_u(i)$ and user feature vector f_i at time $t_u(i)$. Taken into account G , we considered a collection of all commenters for each user $u \in V$, which denoted as a $Z_u = \{v | (u, v) \in E\}$. The size of the commenters set Z_u is $n(u)$. In addition, $A_i \in \{0, 1\}^{n_k \times n_k}$ is an adjacency matrix.

Both emotion signal (publisher and social) is composed of a variety of features extracted from news contents, including the emotion category, emotional lexicon and emotion score features. For the user feature vector f_i , we use several commonly adopted attributes to describe user characteristics, including the number of followers, number of friends, follower–friend ratio, number of historical tweets, number of historical comments, number of historical favourites, and account verification status.

2.2 DualEmo Feature Extraction

Publisher Emotion. The length L of tweet content is represented as a set of words $Q=\{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_L\}$, where w_i is the i^{th} keyword of the text and the corresponding emotion feature emo_Q^{Pub} .

For *emotion category* emo^{cate} , we have adopted a well-known Russell circumplex model of affect [17,5] that encompasses eight primary emotions $S_u(i)$: *Disgust, Anger, Surprise, Happy, Serene, Relaxed, Fatigued and Sad*. According to this model, every affective experience is defined by *valence* v and *arousal* a coordinate in the 2D circumplex. We also use two sentiment polarities (positive and negative), which are widely recognized as the prototypical and foundational dimensions of human emotion [14].

For the *emotional lexicon* emo^{lex} , we have adopted well-grounded NRC VAD Lexicon v2 [13] to increase the coverage of the text which has more than 55,000 English words and phrases. It provides valence and arousal value for unique emotion word in English.

To estimate the *emotional score* emo^{score} , we calculate the valence and arousal values of each emotional word contained in the dictionary. Given the tweet content, we carefully aggregate the score of v_e and a_e each emotional words w_e from the whole text. The overall emotional score emo^{score} for the valence v_e and arousal a_e of a content defined in the Equation 1:

$$emo^{score} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N v_i}{N} \quad (1)$$

where $emo_{v_e}^{score} \in emo^{score}$ is the mean value of valence (similarly, $emo_{a_e}^{score}$ mean value of arousal), N is the total number of emotional words within the message.

For the *Publisher Emotion*, we concatenate all three kinds of features described above and obtain emo_Q^{Pub} , as shown in Equation 2:

$$emo_Q^{Pub} = emo^{cate} \oplus emo^{lex} \oplus emo^{score} \quad (2)$$

Social Emotion. We first extract the social emotion emo_Q^{Soc} from the comments associated with a news piece and then aggregate these signals to form a unified representation. The emotional state for each comment is calculated in the same way as the publisher emotion emo_Q^{Pub} by using Equation2, denoted as emo_r^{Pub} and calculate the score of the entire comment set emo_Q^{Soc} through Equation3:

$$emo_Q^{Soc} = emo_{r_1}^{Pub} \oplus emo_{r_2}^{Pub} \oplus \dots \oplus emo_{r_n}^{Pub} \quad (3)$$

After getting emo_Q^{Soc} , we consider two aggregators to generate the *Social Emotion* of the whole comments list: 1) mean pooling for representing the average emotional signals (Equation4); and 2) max pooling for capturing the extreme emotional signals (Equation5).

$$emo_Q^{Soc^{mean}} = mean(emo_Q^{Soc}) \quad (4)$$

$$emo_Q^{Soc^{max}} = \max(emo_Q^{Soc}) \quad (5)$$

Finally, for the *Social Emotion*, we concatenate mean and max pooling together and obtain emo_Q^{Soc} , as shown in Equation6:

$$emo_Q^{Soc} = emo_Q^{Soc^{mean}} \oplus emo_Q^{Soc^{max}} \quad (6)$$

Emotion Difference. To highlight the emotional differences between authors and reviewers of dual emotion, we propose *Emotion Difference* (denoted as emo^{diff}). It is designed as the subtraction between publisher and social emotion. As shown in Equation7, emo^{diff} is concatenated by the difference of emo_Q^{Pub} and two different parts, average emotion $emo_Q^{Soc^{mean}}$ and the extreme sentiment $emo_Q^{Soc^{max}}$:

$$emo^{diff} = (emo_Q^{Pub} - emo_Q^{Soc^{mean}}) \oplus (emo_Q^{Pub} - emo_Q^{Soc^{max}}) \quad (7)$$

Dual Emotion Features. Finally, *Dual Emotion Features* emo^{dual} are concatenated by the publisher emotion emo_Q^{Pub} , the social emotion emo_Q^{Soc} and the emotion difference emo^{diff} . It is generated as shown in Equation8:

$$Emo^{dual} = emo_Q^{Pub} \oplus emo_Q^{Soc} \oplus emo^{diff} \quad (8)$$

2.3 Semantic Feature Extraction

In the proposed framework, we utilize word embeddings and employ BERT to extract semantic feature representations. The multi-head self-attention mechanism in the BERT model effectively mitigates the challenge of overlooking meaningful context, generating feature vectors that accurately capture both the literal and contextual semantics of the text.

The length n of the content is represented as a set of words $Q = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$, where w_i is the i^{th} keyword of the text and the corresponding feature vector set $K = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ is obtained through the BERT pre-processing model, where v_i is the word vector corresponding to the feature word w_i . The initialized text word vectors are submitted to the Transformer model to extract features. The Transformer encoder comprises multiple identical layers, each containing two sub-layers: a multi-head attention mechanism and a feed-forward neural network. The attention mechanism assigns a weight to each word vector to learn the internal dependencies and to extract the text sequence’s internal structural features. The feature vector $(Q, K) \in T$ learned by the multi-headed self-attention layer to feed the feed-forward neural network, and the learned tweet semantic representation vector F_{sem} is obtained as follows:

$$F_{sem} = \max(0, TW_a + b_a) \quad (9)$$

where W_a and b_a are the corresponding weight matrix and bias terms of the feed-forward neural network.

2.4 Structural Feature Extraction

Each node in the propagation structure is associated with an emotion label and a user feature vector. Bi-GCNs [2] are employed to extract temporal propagation information by utilizing both forward-backward and backward-forward operations. The core idea of GCNs is to apply each node to update its features based on its neighbours' features. We employ a novel DropEdge [16] method as a random edge deletion technology to reduce over-fitting for GCN-based models during the training state. Formally, suppose the total number of edges in the graph A is N_e and the dropping rate is p , then the adjacency matrix after DropEdge, A' , is computed as below:

$$A' = A - A_{drop} \quad (10)$$

where A_{drop} is a matrix structure randomly sampled from the original edge set using $N_e \times p$. At each training epoch, p percentage of edges are dropped via Eq. (10) to form A' , which avoid penitential over-fitting issues. In our Bi-GCNs model, we construct two network components: *Forward Chain Graph Convolutional Networks* (FC-GCNs) and *Backward Chain Graph Convolutional Networks* (BC-GCNs). For FC-GCNs, the adjacency matrix is represented as $A^{FC} = A'$, while for BC-GCNs, the adjacency matrix is $A^{BC} = A'$. The FC-GCNs and the BC-GCNs obtain the propagation and diffusion features, respectively. The equation of the FC-GCNs is as follows:

$$HL^{(FC)} = \sigma(A^{FC} \times W^{FC}) \quad (11)$$

where $HL^{(FC)} \in R^{n \times v}$ is the hidden layer feature, W^{FC} is the filter parameter matrix of FC-GCNs, σ is the ReLU activation function, and the equation of the BC-GCNs is as follows:

$$HL^{(BC)} = \sigma(A^{BC} \times W^{BC}) \quad (12)$$

where $HL^{(BC)} \in R^{n \times v}$ is the hidden layer feature, W^{BC} is the filter parameter matrix of BC-GCNs. The representations of propagation and diffusion are the aggregations from the node representations of FC-GCNs and BC-GCNs, respectively. Here, we employ mean-pooling operators to aggregate information from these two sets of node representations. It is formulated as follows:

$$\hat{HL}^{(FC)} = Mean(HL^{(FC)}) \quad (13)$$

$$\hat{HL}^{(BC)} = Mean(HL^{(BC)}) \quad (14)$$

Finally, after obtaining the feature vectors for the FC-GCNs and BC-GCNs, we concatenate the representations of propagation and the representation of dispersion to merge the information of structural feature F_{str} as follows:

$$F_{str} = \hat{HL}^{(FC)} \oplus \hat{HL}^{(BC)} \quad (15)$$

2.5 Fake News Detection

Finally, we concatenate the dual emotional features Emo^{dual} , semantic features F_{sem} , and propagation structure features F_{str} into a unified representation F_{uni} , which serves as the fused input for jointly predicting the veracity of *Fake/Real* news \hat{V} .

$$F_{uni} = Emo^{dual} \oplus F_{sem} \oplus F_{str} \quad (16)$$

Finally, the output layer of DE-FIND employs a *Softmax* function to generate the probability distribution for fake news detection.

$$\hat{V} = Softmax(F_{uni} + b) \quad (17)$$

3 Experiments

3.1 Experimental Setup

Dataset Descriptions. We evaluate our proposed method by using a publicly available datasets such as *RumorEval-19* [7] and *PHEME* [23] to focus on detecting fake and real news. The dataset *RumorEval-19* contains Twitter and Reddit discussions about rumours, and the source tweet expresses a rumour or non-rumour and related comments linked to the news event. Each news piece is annotated as fake, real, or unverified with related ground truth. Here, we retain only fake (138 contents, 2,648 comments) and real (185 contents, 3,114 comments). Similarly, the *PHEME* dataset supports binary fake-news classification by providing tweets (news) and their corresponding user comments. It comprises Twitter threads from nine major news events, including the Charlie Hebdo, Sydney Siege, Prince Toronto, Ferguson, Putin Missing, German Wings Crash, Gurlitt, Ebola Essien and the Otta was shooting. Each thread begins with an original news tweet followed by a sequence of user comments. In our study, we utilize the original news tweet together with all associated comments, comprising fake (126 contents, 2,222 comments) and real (170 contents, 1,780 comments). Both datasets are split into training, validation, and test sets in a 3:1:1 ratio.

Baselines and Evaluation Metrics. To validate our model, we adopt two baseline emotion features, namely EmoCred [6] and Dual Emotion [22], to assess the effectiveness of emotion identification. On the other hand, to evaluate the capability of text-based fake news detectors, we employ Bi-GCN [2] and BERT [4] as comparative baselines along with our simplified version of the (DuelEmo \cup Semantic \cup Structural) DE-FIND model. We adopt Accuracy, Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and F1 score as the evaluation metrics for both datasets.

Model Parameters. The model is implemented using a deep learning framework and trained on a single GPU. We employ the Adam optimizer [1] for parameter optimization with an initial learning rate of 2×10^{-5} for the BERT

component and 1×10^{-3} for the remaining network modules, including Bi-GRU and Bi-GCN. A mini-batch size of 32 is used during training to balance computational efficiency and memory constraints. The model is trained for 20–30 epochs, and early stopping is applied based on validation performance to prevent over-fitting. Dropout regularization is used with a rate of 0.3–0.5 in the Bi-GRU and fusion layers. All trainable parameters are initialized using standard initialization strategies provided by the framework.

3.2 Experimental Result and Analysis

Table 1 presents the performance comparison of the proposed DE-FIND framework against two baseline detectors (Bi-GCN and BERT) and their variants augmented with emotion features (EmoCred and Dual Emotion) on two benchmark datasets, RumorEval-19 and PHEME. Across the two datasets, the model performs comparatively well on test set.

Table 1. Result on RumorEval-19 and PHEME

Models	RumorEval-19				PHEME			
	Acc.	RMSE	F ₁ – Score		Acc.	RMSE	F ₁ – Score	
			Fake	Real			Fake	Real
Bi-GCN	0.819	0.794	0.519	0.304	0.786	0.710	0.487	0.275
+ EmoCred	0.842	0.786	0.501	0.364	0.814	0.699	0.496	0.279
+ Dual Emotion	0.857	0.742	0.583	0.379	0.842	0.681	0.489	0.276
BERT	0.834	0.788	0.533	0.105	0.869	0.666	0.504	0.287
+ EmoCred	0.847	0.765	0.367	0.367	0.879	0.649	0.523	0.321
+ Dual Emotion	0.876	0.778	0.557	0.224	0.871	0.655	0.521	0.317
DE-FIND	0.882	0.733	0.596	0.382	0.889	0.649	0.582	0.321

On the RumorEval-19 dataset, Bi-GCN and BERT achieve baseline accuracies of 0.819 and 0.834, respectively. The inclusion of EmoCred slightly improves performance (0.842 and 0.847), while Dual Emotion provides further gains (0.857 and 0.876). In contrast, DE-FIND delivers the best results across all metrics, achieving 0.882 accuracy and the lowest RMSE of 0.733, alongside the highest F1-scores for both Fake (0.596) and Real (0.382) classes. These results demonstrate the ability of DE-FIND to effectively integrate dual emotional, semantic, and structural features for more accurate detection.

A similar trend is observed in the PHEME dataset. While BERT achieves a strong baseline accuracy of 0.869, DE-FIND surpasses all baselines with an accuracy of 0.889. Moreover, it achieves a competitive RMSE (0.649) and significantly higher F1-scores for Fake (0.582) and Real (0.321) compared to other approaches. The balanced improvement across both classes highlights the robustness of DE-FIND in handling real-world misinformation detection tasks.

According to the results, integrating Bi-GCN and BERT fake news detectors with *EmoCred* and *Dual Emotion* features significantly improves performance. But our simplified *DE-FIND* model, which integrates both semantic and structural features, significantly achieves better performance than EmoCred and Dual

Emotion. This demonstrates the effectiveness of feature fusion in enhancing fake news detection. More specifically, our model outperforms baseline methods on both datasets, achieving accuracy improvements of at least 1.2% and 1.5%, respectively. However, when using *EmoCred* and *Dual Emotion* on Bi-GCN, sometimes the metrics even decrease. It reveals that *EmoCred* and *Dual Emotion* are more likely to be over-fitted, since *EmoCred* focus on the contents alone but ignore the comments and the *Dual Emotion* jointly can avoid this situation to some extent but ignore temporal structural information.

Overall, DE-FIND consistently outperforms all baselines, achieving at least +1.2% and +1.5% accuracy improvements on RumorEval-19 and PHEME, respectively. Importantly, the framework not only improves overall accuracy but also enhances class-specific F1-scores, addressing the common issue of class imbalance in fake news detection. These results confirm that the joint modelling of dual emotional, semantic, and structural signals provides a more comprehensive and effective approach to fake news detection and emotion identification in social media contexts. Although precision and recall are not explicitly reported, the improvements in F1-score indicate a better balance between precision and recall, particularly for the fake news class. The superior F1 performance of DE-FIND suggests that the proposed framework effectively reduces both false positives and false negatives. Consequently, in this work, we emphasize class-wise F1-scores alongside accuracy to provide a comprehensive and fair evaluation of model effectiveness in detecting fake news across imbalanced datasets such as RumorEval-19 and PHEME.

4 Conclusion

This paper introduces a deep learning framework, termed *DE-FIND*, which leverages multiple feature components to detect fake news on social networks. The framework systematically incorporates temporal propagation features, dual emotional signals, and semantic representations. Experimental results demonstrate that combining these mechanisms substantially enhances model performance. Nonetheless, there remains considerable scope for improvement by integrating additional contextual features from diverse dimensions.

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